

Understanding local adaptation to prepare populations for climate change

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1 **Abstract:**

2 Adaptation within species to local environments is widespread in nature. Better
3 understanding this local adaptation is critical to conserving biodiversity. However,
4 conservation practices can rely on species' trait averages, or broadly assume
5 homogeneity across the range, to inform management. Recent methodological
6 advances for studying local adaptation provide the opportunity to fine-tune efforts for
7 managing and conserving species. Implementation of these advances will allow us to
8 better identify populations at greatest risk of decline due to climate change, as well as
9 highlight possible strategies for improving the likelihood of population persistence
10 amidst climate change. Here, we review recent advances in the study of local
11 adaptation and highlight ways these tools can be applied in conservation efforts.
12 Cutting-edge tools are available to help better identify and characterize local adaptation.
13 Indeed, increased incorporation of local adaptation in management decisions may help
14 meet imminent demands of managing species amidst a rapidly changing world.

15 **I. Local adaptation (LA) can be better incorporated in conservation efforts**

16 **Local adaptation** (Williams 2018) is pervasive across ecological systems, and is a key
17 evolutionary process that has generated much of the world's biodiversity. LA is the
18 process by which populations have traits that confer higher survival and reproduction in
19 the local environment compared to elsewhere due to the spatial match between
20 adaptive genetic variation and environmental variation (Blanquart *et al.* 2013). LA is
21 generally a result of divergent selection over one or more traits, which, if combined with

22 geographical isolation, can lead to different evolutionary trajectories, including
23 reproductive isolation and speciation (White and Butlin 2021). LA has been widely
24 investigated across the tree of life (e.g. Kawecki and Ebert 2004; Blanquart *et al.* 2013),
25 and we are rapidly increasing our understanding of the scale and pervasiveness of LA
26 (Sork 2017).

27 As our understanding of the processes that generate and maintain diversity has rapidly
28 expanded, so has our interest in the consequences of LA (Hereford 2009; Savolainen *et al.*
29 *al.* 2013). One of the most-important outcomes of LA may be the maintenance of
30 ecologically important genetic variation, which can be vital for species' persistence
31 amidst changing ecological conditions (Whitlock 2015). However, much of the spatial
32 variability in adaptive genetic diversity generated by LA may be threatened by the
33 multifaceted effects of global and anthropogenic change. Additionally, adaptation to
34 non-climatic factors, such as other abiotic and biotic interactions (e.g., soil and water
35 characteristics, diseases, food resources, predation, and competition), may be disrupted
36 by climate change (Delph 2017). A shift from local adaptation to maladaptation (i.e.,
37 reduced fitness and survival of individuals, given a mismatch between genetically
38 determined traits and the current environment) under fast-changing environments likely
39 contributes to staggering losses of populations worldwide (Derry *et al.* 2019). Thus, an
40 improved understanding of LA can help guide conservation actions to better conserve
41 the world's biodiversity (e.g., Fig. 1). One caveat in this discussion of LA and
42 conservation, however, is that in extremely small populations, the larger forces of
43 genetic drift and mutational load may prevent local adaptation from occurring (Willi *et al.*
44 2022). Therefore, managers in such situations may find more benefit from focusing on

45 increasing overall genetic diversity and census size (Willi *et al.* 2022). Information on
46 LA, however, can provide valuable insights for improving the adaptive potential of
47 populations that are not on the very brink of extinction, to maximize their likelihood of
48 long-term persistence (Bay *et al.* 2018; Flanagan *et al.* 2018). Additionally, utilizing LA
49 to inform translocations, reintroductions, captive breeding, and identification of
50 conservation units and critical habitat may substantially increase the likelihood of
51 successful outcomes (Flanagan *et al.* 2018). Despite this importance, relatively few
52 studies have incorporated LA into predictions of how species' distributions and
53 abundances will be affected by climate change (Smith *et al.* 2019) or taken LA into
54 account when designing conservation and recovery plans (Peterson *et al.* 2019).

55 The time is ripe to evaluate LA as a standard component of conservation planning and
56 integrate it into conservation actions (Hellmann and Pfrender 2011). Herein, our
57 objectives are to provide a primer on LA and its potential incorporation in conservation
58 by: 1) highlighting the ways conservation biologists can merge classic and emerging
59 tools to detect LA; 2) exemplifying methods for incorporating LA in conservation actions
60 to better help populations withstand changing climate and other ecological stressors;
61 and 3) describing the implications and applications of LA to policy, management, and
62 conservation and future directions for promoting the strategic incorporation of LA into
63 conservation decision-making. We acknowledge that numerous other ecological
64 disturbances (e.g., land-use change, over-harvest, pollution, disease) have all
65 contributed to losses of biodiversity (Díaz *et al.* 2019). Given this, we primarily focus
66 here on climate change because of its iteratively increasing pace, near-ubiquity,

67 interaction with the above-mentioned factors, and clear influence on fitness and
68 population persistence.

69 **II. Integrating classic and emerging tools to characterize and quantify LA**

70 Common-garden experiments and reciprocal transplants have been the gold standard
71 for identifying LA and separating genetic contributions from phenotypic plasticity.

72 However, these studies tend to be biased toward abundant, well-studied, easy-to-
73 translocate species, and parsing traits with complex genetic architecture requires using
74 many study individuals (Ghalambor *et al.* 2018). Until recently, this limited the ability to
75 incorporate LA in conservation because species of conservation interest are generally
76 understudied and rare, and many traits of conservation interest are likely controlled by a
77 suite of genes, rather than by single genes of strong effect (Savolainen *et al.* 2013).

78 The conservation toolbox is now rapidly expanding as new technologies emerge for
79 studying genomes (i.e., the entirety of an organism's genetic material) and as our
80 understanding of the genomic basis for traits increases. We now have the tools to
81 identify and incorporate LA into conservation and management by integrating cutting-
82 edge genomic data with traditional methods of studying LA, such as common-garden
83 experiments (Hoban *et al.* 2016). We can generate high-resolution genomic data for
84 almost any species (Whitlock 2015). Further, many of these methods do not necessitate
85 rearing or growing organisms in the lab, such as species distribution modeling and
86 landscape genetics, making an understanding of the causes and consequences of LA
87 possible for most organisms of conservation importance (e.g., Fig. 2; Funk *et al.* 2019).
88 We can identify genotypes that are locally adapted, determine the environmental

89 variables driving population differentiation, and pinpoint the genetic variation for specific
90 traits underlying LA, making it possible to then use that information to make predictions
91 for future habitat suitability and guide conservation and restoration actions (Tiffin and
92 Ross-Ibarra 2017). Increasing our understanding of the causes and consequences of
93 LA in species of conservation focus will allow conservation biologists to better
94 understand which populations may be limited in their adaptive potential and how
95 phenotypes and fitness will respond to climate heterogeneity. Ultimately, this
96 information can be used for improved conservation planning. See the **Supplemental**
97 **Table** for further exploration of these methods.

98 **III. Using LA to best equip populations for persistence under changing climates**

99 Given the recent advances in our ability to identify LA, it is now possible to incorporate
100 LA into species conservation and management to plan for future conditions under
101 climate change (Capblancq *et al.* 2020). Managed gene flow and the incorporation of LA
102 in relocation and reintroduction planning each provide options for 'throwing a lifeline' to
103 populations that have become increasingly maladapted to their environment due to
104 reduced genetic diversity or rapidly changing environments, or to restore resilient
105 populations in places where they have become locally extinct. Cryopreservation of
106 gametes and gene editing are two additional technological advances that, if informed by
107 an improved understanding of LA, may provide options for saving species from the brink
108 of extinction and allow a path for protecting species that are most vulnerable to the
109 negative effects of global change. Below, we discuss the benefits and concerns
110 regarding these options and highlight how the understanding of LA can inform these
111 important conservation tools. We are not advocating that these tools should replace

112 more classic conservation strategies, such as land and species protection and take
113 prohibitions, which will continue to constitute pivotal approaches for biodiversity
114 conservation. Rather, we aim to demonstrate that we also now have new tools to
115 combat biodiversity loss.

116 Managed gene flow and translocations/reintroductions

117 Translocation, the human-assisted movement of individuals, has a long history of use in
118 managing populations for conservation objectives (Griffith *et al.* 1989). Today, it can
119 also be a potentially powerful management strategy for mitigating maladaptation due to
120 rapidly changing climate conditions (Hoffmann *et al.* 2021). This can occur through the
121 intentional translocation of individuals within a species' range to reintroduce populations
122 that have gone locally extinct, or to facilitate gene flow of locally adaptive alleles into
123 existing populations. Additionally, locally adapted individuals can be translocated to
124 areas outside their current or historical range that are projected to provide suitable
125 habitat under future climatic conditions based on assessments of adaptive capacity
126 (actions reviewed by Thurman *et al.* 2022).

127 More specifically, translocation is an option for assisted gene flow to benefit maladapted
128 populations and promote increased local adaptation through a number of non-mutually-
129 exclusive mechanisms (Aitken and Whitlock 2013). For example, immigrant genotypes
130 can be sourced from an environment that matches projected future climate conditions,
131 such that "preadapted" alleles are used for translocation or introduction into a
132 maladapted recipient population (Catullo *et al.* 2019, Chen *et al.* 2021). These alleles
133 may be locally adapted to these future conditions. This is most often discussed for long-

134 lived and dispersal-limited species that are unlikely to otherwise keep pace with
135 changes in local climate, such as trees (Browne *et al.* 2019) or corals (Bay and Palumbi
136 2014). A large body of literature also now supports the idea that gene flow into
137 populations that have become small and isolated due to habitat fragmentation can
138 facilitate 'genetic rescue' – an increase in population growth due to the immigration of
139 new genetic material (see Panel). Finally, over a longer timeframe, increased genetic
140 variation provided by assisted gene flow may be a critical source of raw genetic material
141 that allows populations to adapt to novel selection pressures (Derry *et al.* 2019).

142 Although assisted gene flow and movement of individuals have many potential benefits,
143 they also pose a number of possible risks. Outbreeding depression can occur if
144 immigrants are too distantly related (particularly if they have differences in chromosomal
145 structure or number) and/or if they introduce traits that are not well-suited for the new
146 environment (Frankham *et al.* 2011; Leroy *et al.* 2018). For example, reduced hybrid
147 survival was observed when geographically separated salmon populations with distinct
148 spawning phenotypes (even- vs odd-year spawn timing) were crossed (Gilk *et al.* 2004),
149 highlighting the critical importance of a strong understanding of organismal natural
150 history before carrying out assisted gene flow. Another concern is loss of local genetic
151 lineages through genetic swamping (Rhymer and Simberloff 1996; Gilk *et al.* 2004).
152 This may occur if too many individuals with higher fitness than local individuals are
153 introduced. It has also been shown that strong selection can maintain locally favored
154 alleles, even in the face of high gene flow (Fitzpatrick *et al.* 2020). Although the benefits
155 of assisted gene flow and genetic rescue within a species' range are increasingly
156 recognized, movement of individuals to areas outside of the historical range of a

157 species should be treated cautiously (Schwartz *et al.* 2012). Thus, building on the
158 lessons from empirical studies, demographic modeling and simulations are increasingly
159 used as powerful tools to both 1) forecast the interaction of LA with demographic, biotic
160 and abiotic factors (Landguth *et al.* 2020), and 2) predict the spatial distribution of
161 adaptive genetic variants and thus, determine appropriate current and future geographic
162 areas for translocations (Razgour *et al.* 2019; Rochat *et al.* 2021). Simulations of
163 assisted gene flow have shown that multiple translocations over several generations
164 can lead to smaller reductions of fitness, especially if outbreeding depression is strong
165 (Grummer *et al.* 2021). However, when traits are polygenic (i.e., controlled by multiple
166 loci of small effect), the beneficial effects of assisted gene flow may only be tangible on
167 a longer time scale than that necessary for most climate-related actions (Grummer *et al.*
168 2021). Given that “the stage” and “evolutionary play” are iteratively changing as noted
169 by G.E. Hutchinson, conservation practitioners must also ensure that viability of source
170 populations is not compromised by assisted migration. These above-described
171 concerns deserve increased research to continue to increase the applicability of this
172 important conservation tool (Fitzpatrick *et al.* 2020; Brodie *et al.* 2021).

173 Cryopreservation and seed banking

174 Another emerging tool that can be used to help support incorporation of LA in
175 conservation is seed banking and the cryopreservation (freezing) of gametes, embryos,
176 or somatic cells (Fig. 3). These methods have been increasingly implemented in
177 species where *in-situ* conservation methods have failed to maintain viable populations
178 (Holt *et al.* 1996; Ryder and Onuma 2018). There are around 1,300 seed banks world-
179 wide, and ecologists are gaining an understanding of how best to design and sample

180 populations to increase the utility of seed banks for promoting LA (Rajasekharan 2015;
181 Hoban 2019). Additionally, there have been rapid advances in cryopreservation
182 techniques that allow maintenance of genetic material for animals and plants (e.g.,
183 tropical species) whose seed can't be stored (e.g., maintenance of tissue culture stocks;
184 Ryder and Onuma 2018). Cryopreserved cells can theoretically be stored indefinitely,
185 and can serve as "back-ups" to preserve the genotypes of individuals. When combined
186 with *in-vitro* fertilization techniques, this approach can produce new offspring (Charlton
187 *et al.* 2018; Ryder and Onuma 2018), which may then be used in genetic-rescue and
188 reintroduction efforts.

189 Seed banks and cryopreserved cells not only serve as genetic resource banks to
190 conserve genetic diversity overall in an imperiled species, but can also preserve locally
191 adapted genotypes that are important for future adaptive potential (Holt *et al.* 1996). In
192 black-footed ferrets, a species reliant on *ex-situ* conservation and whose extremely low
193 population sizes have led to strong inbreeding effects, the use of frozen spermatozoa
194 and artificial-insemination techniques increased genetic diversity and lowered measures
195 of inbreeding in released individuals (Howard *et al.* 2016). This approach can be
196 combined with genomic analyses to identify and target genetic variants that are, or will
197 be, important for promoting LA. The northern white rhinoceros is extinct in the wild, but
198 cells from multiple individuals have been cryopreserved. These cells have been tested
199 not only for measures of genetic diversity, but also signatures of selection that may
200 reflect locally adapted genotypes (Tunstall *et al.* 2018). These data can be used to
201 prioritize cells that will lead to offspring with the greatest chance of success in the
202 reintroduction effort (Howard *et al.* 2016; Tunstall *et al.* 2018). This approach was

203 recently proven successful by cloning an individual black-footed ferret from cells that
204 had been cryopreserved for over 30 years (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 2021a).
205 Promoting LA amidst ongoing global change via cryopreservation might specifically
206 include: a) ensuring that individuals from disjunct populations are well represented; b)
207 including individuals from numerous edges of the bioclimatic envelope (or that have
208 wide moisture and temperature tolerances), particularly from trailing-edge populations;
209 c) preserving populations that naturally experienced higher frequencies of extreme
210 events; d) including individuals from transition zones; and e) including individuals from
211 more populations of poorly dispersing species associated with past climates, such as
212 cryosphere-associated species (Thurman et al. 2022). However, it will be important to
213 also ensure any of these targets of cryopreservation also come from populations with
214 high levels of overall genomic diversity to avoid the negative effects of bottlenecks.

215 Cryopreservation, however, requires technical knowledge from specialist veterinarians
216 and regular maintenance at designated facilities. Additionally, there is significant
217 variation among species in the viability of frozen gametes for fertilization (Charlton *et al.*
218 2018; Ryder and Onuma 2018). Cryopreservation has also been shown to have
219 negative effects on the morphology of some species, including effects that can reduce
220 the survivorship and reproductive output of individuals (Poo and Hinkson 2020).

221 Nonetheless, seed banks and ‘frozen zoos’ may be the last option for the future of some
222 species, and research on how to improve seed banking and cryopreservation
223 techniques to support future adaptation seems poised to provide invaluable insights.

224 Gene editing

225 Gene-editing technology has also emerged as a potentially viable tool for conservation
226 biology in recent years, especially with the explosion of versatile CRISPR gene-editing
227 techniques (Phelps *et al.* 2020). An example of gene-editing utility for conservation can
228 be found in the 'iwi (Hawaiian honeycreeper). Simulation models of 'iwi
229 reintroductions after devastating population loss driven by non-native malaria suggest
230 that the species has a much higher chance of success if genetically edited, malaria-
231 resistant individuals were to be introduced (Samuel *et al.* 2020). Although the 'iwi has
232 not yet been gene-edited, this study demonstrates the strong potential for this tool to
233 assist conservation efforts if a gene for malaria resistance can be identified. This
234 solution is especially important because future warming is projected to increase the rate
235 of malaria-driven extinctions of other species of Hawaiian birds, which may require
236 analogous conservation efforts (Paxton *et al.* 2016). Similar gene-editing schemes have
237 been proposed for other conservation scenarios, such as introducing genes for
238 temperature resistance in coral species, fungal-disease resistance in bats and
239 amphibians, and plague resistance in black-footed ferrets (Piaggio *et al.* 2017). As
240 gene-editing tools become more accessible, and the ability to identify regions of the
241 genome associated with adaptive traits becomes more precise, these technologies will
242 become a more feasible part of the conservation toolkit (Supple and Shapiro 2018;
243 Derry *et al.* 2019). For example, it is not outside the realm of possibility that one day we
244 could identify adaptive genetic variation for thermal tolerance in an organism, using the
245 techniques outlined in the Supplemental Table, and then introduce this variation into
246 populations that will likely need it under future warming, but are currently lacking it,
247 using gene-editing techniques (Thomas *et al.* 2013). This approach could have the

248 added benefit of preserving the unique, local genetic diversity present in the population
249 while introducing important alleles for future persistence. However, as with all the
250 above-mentioned conservation actions, it will be important, and non-trivial, for sufficient
251 overall genetic variation to be produced and maintained in any gene-edited population
252 to avoid inbreeding and promote long-term persistence and resilience. LA-oriented gene
253 editing might specifically include: a) seeking conservation of allelic diversity at multiple
254 spatio-temporal scales; b) seeking maintenance of the evolutionary processes and
255 pathways that maintain LA; and c) balancing concerns about swamping and hybrid vigor
256 with desire to facilitate population persistence in a warmer, drier, and/or more-erratic
257 future climate. Additionally, any use of genome-editing in a conservation context would
258 benefit from being implemented in an adaptive management framework, with sufficient
259 data collection before, during, and after actions, to ensure learning and the possibility
260 for future refinement of techniques.

261 Gene editing also has limitations and requires ethical considerations and community
262 engagement before being implemented as a regular conservation tool (Kardos and
263 Shafer 2018, Barnhill-Dilling and Delborne 2021). Gene-editing technologies have
264 progressed rapidly, but still depend on the ability to accurately identify regions of the
265 genome that are adaptive and loci that have large effects on the trait of interest (Phelps
266 *et al.* 2020). This approach is unlikely to work well for traits that are determined by many
267 loci of small effect. In addition, there is some public resistance to the use of gene-editing
268 technologies for conservation purposes, and many people remain skeptical that the
269 techniques are safe and/or ethical (Kohl *et al.* 2019). Thus, it is important to engage with
270 multiple stakeholders when considering genetically modifying organisms for

271 conservation purposes (Kofler *et al.* 2018). Ethical analyses of other genomic
272 technologies, such as cloning, have been conducted, and could be adapted to evaluate
273 gene-editing as well (Sandler *et al.* 2021). Additionally, we presume that specific
274 policies around the use of gene-editing for conservation will be developed iteratively
275 over time (Burgiel *et al.* 2021). Although the practical and ethical considerations of gene
276 editing should be carefully weighed, this technology may constitute the last chance for
277 species when all other conservation efforts have failed. Conservation biologists may
278 benefit from increasing engagement with these emerging technologies to reduce future
279 biodiversity loss and plan for future climatic conditions (Piaggio *et al.* 2017).

280 **IV. Implications and applications for policy, management, and conservation**

281 LA has profound implications for a wide array of conservation actions, as described
282 above. However, the full incorporation of LA into the conservation toolbox will require
283 both emphasizing the identification of LA and having policies that promote the
284 incorporation of LA in conservation planning (Hällfors *et al.* 2016). This includes having
285 flexibility in the legal and regulatory mechanisms for preserving biodiversity under future
286 climate conditions, while also providing clear directives. The European Union's Birds
287 and Habitats Directive, for instance, provides regulatory agencies numerous options for
288 planning and implementing actions to assist natural populations with adaptation to
289 climate change. This flexibility, however, also has its limitations, as it does not require
290 any specific actions or protections; consequently, planning for climate change is
291 possible but voluntary (Verschuuren 2010).

292 Genomic advances are reshaping how we identify conservation units. There is ongoing
293 vigorous debate among scientists and practitioners regarding how to weigh patterns
294 shown in a small number of genes versus genome-wide patterns in conservation
295 decisions and policy (Teixeira and Huber 2021; Kardos *et al.* 2021; Waples *et al.* 2022).
296 For example, genomic research has recently identified one genomic region (GREB1L to
297 ROCK1) as being tightly linked with migration timing, an important life-history trait driven
298 by LA, in Pacific salmon (Prince *et al.* 2017; Waples and Lindley 2018). Researchers
299 have demonstrated dramatic reductions in diversity at this locus after anthropogenic
300 habitat modification, potentially reducing fitness and population sustainability
301 (Thompson *et al.* 2019). Other components of fitness in salmonids, however, including
302 growth rate and age at maturity, appear to be less homogeneous in their genetic basis
303 (Waters *et al.* 2018). Consequently, it can be challenging to determine how much weight
304 should be given to single genomic regions versus genome-wide patterns when
305 designing conservation actions, particularly given that overall genomic diversity will
306 provide the building blocks for future adaptation (García-Dorado and Caballero 2021;
307 DeWoody *et al.* 2021).

308 Assisted gene flow and assisted colonization, as discussed above, are potentially
309 powerful methods for helping dispersal-limited species to cope with climate change and
310 increase overall genetic diversity (Williams *et al.* 2021). However, for assisted gene flow
311 and assisted colonization to become effective policy, clear protocols and benchmarks
312 will be needed to guide when and how translocations can occur (Schwartz *et al.* 2012).
313 Translocations triggered by clear population declines, high likelihood of future declines,
314 or loss of ecosystem function are consistent with the preventive principle (addressing

315 known ongoing declines in threatened species) and precautionary principle (addressing
316 anticipated or hypothetical future declines) outlined by the Rio Declaration on
317 Environment and Development (Sansilvestri *et al.* 2015).

318 In addition to directly assisting movement, another critical component of conservation
319 planning relevant to local adaptation is reserve design that helps assist movement
320 through human-dominated habitats, assuming that organisms (and their associated
321 traits) can disperse sufficiently quickly (Kostyack *et al.* 2011). Reserves can be
322 designed to both promote movement between important habitats and to conserve the
323 highest number of adaptively differentiated populations. Reserve design and
324 conservation planning can combine methods for identifying and mapping out local
325 adaptation (outlined in Section II above) with spatial analyses of climate refugia (see
326 Saunders *et al.* 2022, Stralberg *et al.* 2020, Michalak *et al.* 2020) to prioritize areas for
327 protection. For example, Saunders *et al.* (2022) conduct a reserve-selection
328 prioritization to highlight priority areas for reserve design that both complement the
329 current protected area network and would protect climate refugia for the highest number
330 of taxonomic groups. One could expand on this analysis further to ensure adaptively
331 differentiated populations within species are represented across the reserve network.
332 Such combinations would improve our ability to conserve adaptive variation that will be
333 important for species persistence now and into the future.

334 Under national laws aimed at species conservation, such as the USA's Endangered
335 Species Act (ESA), addressing extant conventional threats has arguably often garnered
336 higher priority than pre-emptive management in the face of climate change (Delach *et*

337 *al.* 2019). Nonetheless, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) is evaluating (as of
338 Nov. 2021) use of techniques such as translocations, reintroductions, genetic
339 supplementation of *in-situ* populations, and use of captive breeding to create *ex-situ*
340 insurance populations and 'head-starting' of offspring for numerous species whose
341 range has become markedly more fragmented than the historical range and for which
342 local adaptation was used to help delineate conservation or recovery units (e.g., rusty-
343 patched bumble bee (USFWS 2021b), Eastern massasauga rattlesnake (USFWS
344 2021c), Dakota skipper (USFWS 2019)). Such actions seek to achieve persistence of
345 locally adapted populations across diverse selective regimes, higher genetic diversity,
346 avoidance of inbreeding depression, and long-term persistence amidst increasingly
347 stochastic environmental conditions. Analogously, given declining population sizes and
348 declining heterozygosity, and after considering risks of genetic swamping and loss of
349 local adaptation, translocations of numerous mountain pygmy possum (an endangered
350 Australian marsupial) individuals from a genetically diverged population achieved
351 genetic rescue and demographic recovery of 1 of the 3 remaining extant populations of
352 the species (Weeks et al. 2017).

353 The IUCN Guidelines for Reintroductions and Other Conservation Translocations (IUCN
354 2013) can be used for developing national and more-localized guidance for using these
355 tools amidst climate change. The Guidelines acknowledge the importance of information
356 on adaptations to local ecological conditions, yet many other factors also warrant
357 attention when considering human-assisted movement of individuals for conservation.
358 Similarly, Weeks et al. (2011) provided pragmatic decision trees to evaluate possible
359 translocations (see Fig. 2, Table 2), suggesting that local adaptation would constitute

360 one of seven suites of factors governing the likelihood of both resilience and persistence
361 of translocated populations. Determining whether and how translocated individuals will
362 be moved may require modification of existing laws and/or policies. For example, the
363 ESA provisions governing the movement of endangered or threatened plants are
364 currently much less restrictive than those for animals, and may warrant new or revised
365 guidelines or policy to be able to apply more broadly to animals (Shirey and Lamberti
366 2010). Aitken and Whitlock (2013) argued in their incisive review that to robustly weigh
367 the risks of translocations (i.e., outbreeding depression and disrupting local adaptation
368 to non-climatic factors) against their ability to mitigate maladaptation due to climate
369 change, both pattern of gene flow and extent of LA need to be known.

370 Looking forward, conservation actions necessitating and enabling the movement of
371 individuals and genes due to climate change-induced shifts in suitable habitat will at
372 times require collaboration among multiple governmental and non-governmental
373 organizations, and in many cases across national boundaries. Current transboundary
374 agreements for climate change often fail to accommodate this reality (Trouwborst 2012).
375 A logical early step for transboundary collaborations would involve synthesizing data
376 gathered by scientists and managers across species' ranges to identify patterns of LA.
377 This approach can help in 1) assessing potential benefits and risks of assisted migration
378 or colonization across borders to reduce extinction risk, 2) approaching reserve design
379 at a continental scale, 3) identifying alleles associated with higher fitness under different
380 climatic conditions, and 4) determining populations for which seed
381 banking/cryopreservation ought to be given high priority to preserve options for future
382 conservation efforts. Organizations such as zoos, botanical gardens, or biobanks

383 involved in cryopreservation or captive propagation of threatened species constitute key
384 partners in coordinating efforts and providing genetic material or individuals for
385 translocations. Additionally, the resources required to prepare populations for climate-
386 change threats will be much greater than the resources available to meet the need for
387 all taxa threatened by climate change. Consequently, conservation practitioners will
388 necessarily have to prioritize actions and employ cost-benefit analyses to inform when
389 to apply these tools. Collaborations across the researcher-practitioner-policy spectrum
390 may be beneficial to help managers identify the best combination of strategies, tools,
391 and resources for adaptively managing species with local adaptation in mind.

392 **V. Conclusions**

393 We now have the technical capabilities to meaningfully integrate local adaptation (LA)
394 into conservation planning. Although taking an LA-focused conservation approach may
395 necessitate greater initial investment in funds and human resources, we believe taking
396 this approach will often have large returns on investment in terms of higher mean
397 fitness, long-term sustainability, and greater effectiveness in buffering against the
398 negative effects of climate change. Thorough and nuanced understanding of local
399 adaptation is increasingly pivotal to inform the climate-adaptation conservation and
400 management actions described herein, such as assisted migration, seed sourcing for
401 restoration, active management of fragmented metapopulations and low-dispersal
402 species, identification of conservation units, reserve design, and more-accurate
403 predictions of climate-mediated range shifts. Indeed, LA tools and approaches may
404 provide the best last-ditch option for some species, such as those with long generation

405 times, and/or limited and infrequent gene flow. We acknowledge, however, that LA-
406 relevant data are lacking for many species, including climate-sensitive species and
407 despite massive advances in tools, data, and analytical approaches, numerous
408 research frontiers remain. The climatic factors and mechanisms involved, critical life-
409 stages, and population dynamics most strongly affecting persistence can be unknown,
410 for parts or all of a species' range. In such cases, prioritizing the collection of such data
411 could reap large rewards, and it is our hope that the information provided in our
412 Supplemental table can help in that data generation process. Ultimately, land and
413 wildlife managers and other conservation practitioners must weave LA information into
414 an amalgamation of climate-change vulnerability involving not only adaptive capacity,
415 but also sensitivity, exposure, and anthropogenic disturbances. Indeed, a recent
416 conceptual framework suggested that a primary pathway for reducing a species'
417 adaptive capacity (including its evolutionary potential to create LA) from its fundamental
418 to realized level was mediated by extrinsic factors such as pollution, habitat
419 fragmentation, and invasive species (see Fig. 1 of Beever et al. 2016). However, by
420 thoroughly considering LA, conservation practitioners will be better equipped to
421 incorporate the myriad factors involved and prepare populations for long-term
422 persistence under a changing climate.

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429 meeting.

Glossary

Adaptive capacity: the ability of a species or its populations to cope with or accommodate a given change (e.g., climate change) by persisting *in situ* or shifting to more-suitable ranges or microhabitats

Adaptive potential: the ability of a species or population to adapt via evolutionary change

Assisted gene flow: intentional translocation of individuals to facilitate adaptation to anticipated local conditions

Common garden experiment: a method of assessing differential responses to environmental variables by placing two populations into the same environment. Variations of this include reciprocal transplants and provenance plots.

Genetic rescue: an increase in population fitness caused by gene flow inferred from some demographic vital rate or phenotypic trait, by more than can be attributed to the demographic contribution of immigrants

Inbreeding depression: reduced fitness of individuals with related parents due to lower survival and/or reproduction

Maladaptation: Suboptimal fitness, either in absolute terms or relative to another population

Outbreeding depression: reduced fitness (compared to the parental fitness) caused by crossing distantly related individuals

Phenotypic plasticity: in which a single genotype produces multiple phenotypes in response to environmental changes

Reciprocal transplant: a method of evaluating local adaptation by swapping individuals among locations and comparing their fitnesses in their home versus foreign environments. This method requires local and non-local individuals be tested in each habitat of interest, whereas provenance plots do not.

Panel: Does genetic rescue constrain or facilitate local adaptation?

Human-assisted gene flow resulting in genetic rescue has aided the recovery of several iconic species such as Florida panthers (Johnson *et al.* 2010), bighorn sheep (Hogg *et al.* 2006), and Australian marsupials (Weeks *et al.* 2017). Yet, despite increased evidence for its potential to reverse population declines in small and isolated populations, genetic rescue is not a widely used management strategy (Ralls *et al.* 2018). Genetic rescue is primarily thought to increase fitness through masking of deleterious alleles that become exposed in small and inbred populations. However, the genetic architecture underlying genetic rescue is rarely known. In addition to masking deleterious alleles, beneficial genetic variation introduced by gene flow could rescue populations through heterozygote advantage, adaptive evolution, or a combination of these processes (Scott *et al.* 2020).

One of the main concerns with gene-flow augmentation in management is the possibility that gene flow may constrain local adaptation (Edmands 2006). This concern warrants re-evaluation in the context of (1) overwhelming evidence for inbreeding depression when populations become isolated and are rapidly reduced in size; (2) increasing evidence that gene flow increases fitness under a wider set of conditions than what theory predicts (Whiteley *et al.* 2015); and (3) the extent of maladaptation that many

natural populations now face, given the pace of environmental change (Hoffmann and Sgrò 2011). In fact, gene flow may actually facilitate local adaptation, especially in cases where populations lack the variation needed to respond to selection.

Recent empirical work supports the idea that moderate rates of gene flow, even from adaptively differentiated source populations, can maintain or even facilitate adaptation within recipient populations (Panel Figure). For example, experiments using Trinidadian guppies in the wild and in mesocosms showed increases in population growth without the loss of locally adapted traits (Fitzpatrick *et al.* 2016; Kronenberger *et al.* 2018). In fact, gene flow caused shifts in some traits in the predicted adaptive direction (Fitzpatrick *et al.* 2017). In addition, greenhouse crosses using the annual wildflower *Clarkia pulchella* found strongest benefits of gene flow during an anomalously warm year, highlighting the potential role of gene flow in aiding adaptation to warming climates (Bontrager and Angert 2019). As natural populations become fragmented *and* exposed to severe environmental stressors, gene flow may be an increasingly important source of variation necessary for persistence.

A.

B.

C.

D.

Panel Figure

A.

B.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

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Figure Legends:

Panel Figure: A) Trinidad guppies (photo credit: David Herasimtschuk). B) Populations have benefitted from gene flow from adaptively differentiated source populations. Gray arrows indicate initial translocations. Black arrows indicate direction of gene flow. C) Work by Fitzpatrick et al. (2020) showed increases in C) census size after gene flow in both populations. D) Incorporation of new genotypes from translocation is shown by the increase in hybrid index in each population over time.

Figure 1. (A) The importance of incorporating LA in conservation planning is highlighted by research on the American pika (*Ochotona princeps*). A juvenile pika from Darkhorse Creek Canyon, Beaverhead Mountains in the central-northern Rocky Mountain chain, along the Montana-Idaho border. Photo taken by P. Billman, Montana State University. (B) Different populations show different responses to the same range of values in the same climatic aspect. Plot shows the marginal response of each lineage to acute heat days, ignoring the effect of all other variables. Specifically, increasing frequency of hotter days is beneficial to pikas in the northern Rocky Mountains (blue line); it strongly decreases habitat suitability for pikas in the Sierra Nevada (red line); and has no or nearly no effect on pikas in the three other genetic lineages (green, orange, and purple lines). Note that the composite model (black line) masks this intra-specific diversity in how populations respond heterogeneously to climate. Output is from a LARS (least angle regression) model calibrated with an elastic net to obtain the optimal level of regularization. By design, the coefficients are biased toward 0 (unpublished analysis associated with Smith et al. 2019).

Figure 2: (A) Candidate single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) appear tightly linked to temperature in the Willow Flycatcher; the Southwestern Willow Flycatcher has been federally designated as endangered since 1995 (only an estimated 900-1100 pairs existed, as of 2002, USFWS 1995, 2013). Photo credit (A.): V.J. Anderson, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons. (B) As mean temperature of the warmest quarter increases, so does the allele frequency of the temperature-associated SNP. The allele frequencies from the original genome scan data are indicated by squares, whereas allele frequencies based upon the validation set are denoted by circles. The highly significant relationship between this SNP and 7 of the 8 top-ranked climate variables in both the genome scan and validation results suggests a potential role for the SNP in climate adaptation across the region. (C) The geographically explicit representation of panel B, showing the association between Mean Temperature of the Warmest Quarter (BIO10) and the SNP allele frequency across western North America; population allele frequencies are color-coded from high frequency (red) to low (yellow). (D) Map showing the genomic vulnerability (amount of mismatch between current and predicted future genotype-environment relationships) across the Willow Flycatcher breeding range; red=high genomic vulnerability and blue=low genomic vulnerability. Reprinted from Ruegg et al. (2018).

Figure 3: Organisms that have been cryopreserved in order to save genetic material and aid conservation efforts. A) Semen from male Hawaiian ‘alalā is preserved by the

Maui Bird Conservation Center to bank genetic diversity for the recovery effort, photo credit: Lianne Hedditch. B) Black-footed ferret: World Wildlife Fund Northern Great Plains biologist and black-footed ferret expert Kristy Bly prepares to release a black-footed ferret at Snake Butte on the Fort Belknap Reservation, northern Montana. Photo credit: © Clay Bolt / WWF-US. C) San Diego Zoo Global has cells from 12 individual northern white rhinos cryopreserved in the Frozen Zoo® to help recover the species, photo credit: Lianne Hedditch. D) Endangered *Dudleya brevifolia* seed is stored at the San Diego Zoo Wildlife Alliance Native Plant Seed Bank, photo credit: Matthew Luskin, wikimedia.